

Confinement in domestic horses

Social and movement needs of horses

Horses are gregarious animals that live in groups with strong social bonds between conspecifics. They establish stable and long-term relationships, learn from each other, and show synchronised patterns of behavioural activity due to social facilitation. Under natural conditions, horses spend 50-75% of their day walking to find food, water or shelter. When housed in individual boxes, horses are motivated to access a paddock, and are even more motivated when conspecifics are available at the same time.

Horses are often housed in individual boxes to individualise feeding and to limit the risk of injuries caused by conspecifics. In such conditions, a lack of turn-out to paddocks, prolonged confinement and a lack of physical contact with conspecifics can have a negative impact on their welfare.

Legal requirements

Directive 98/58/EC on the protection of animals kept for farming purposes states that:

'The freedom of movement of an animal, having regard to its species and in accordance with established experience and scientific knowledge, must not be restricted in such a way as to cause it unnecessary suffering or injury. Where an animal is continuously or regularly tethered or confined, it must be given the space appropriate to its physiological and ethological needs in accordance with established experience and scientific knowledge.'

(Directive 98/58/EC, Annex, Point 7)

Method to assess the impact on welfare

The restriction of movement or social contacts in horses may have negative impacts on:

- Behaviour
- Physiology and health
- Cognition
- Trainability and safety (for horses and humans)

These impacts can be assessed and measures to improve horses' welfare should be taken to enable appropriate social contacts and freedom of movement.

To know more, see the review '**Confinement, restriction of social contacts and movement in domestic horses**'.

For more details please refer to the **Thematic factsheet 'Confinement in domestic horses.'**

Recommendations for inspection

Key points

1. Horses should not be confined permanently in individual boxes. When horses are confined, they should have visual and tactile contact with conspecifics and they should be turned out daily.
2. Confinement may be required at specific times (e.g. competition, veterinary treatments, quarantine, import).
3. Group housing requires adequate management of groups and space.

During inspection, information on how animals are housed and managed should be collected and animals should be observed to check for absence of abnormal behaviour, aggression between animals or injuries that may result from aggressions.

Collection of information on how animals are housed and managed

Collection of information for horses individually housed

When keeping horses in individual boxes, it is essential that the box is of sufficient size to enable the animals to express lateral recumbency and Rapid Eye Movement (REM) sleep. Minimum individual box dimensions are provided in Table 1. In addition, horses kept in individual boxes must have regular access to a large area for exercise and have contact with conspecifics (Figure 1), except during inclement weather (e.g. orange and red weather alerts) or under veterinary advice.

Table 1: Minimum recommended dimensions of individual boxes for horses

Box properties	Formula for calculating dimensions
Surface (m ²)	$(2 \times \text{horse's height at withers})^2$
Shortest surface's side (m)	$1.5 \times \text{horse's height at withers}$
Ceiling (m)	Horse's height at withers + 1.2

Daily turnout in paddock/pasture with at least one conspecific

Visual and physical interaction between horses (ensuring that horses that are placed next to each other get on well)

Figure 1: Minimum recommendations regarding social interactions and freedom of movement for horses housed in individual boxes. Box dimensions are given as a minimum recommendation for a horse measuring 1.70 m at withers. The green icon represents environmental enrichment.

Collection of information for group-housed horses

Group housing is only successful if there are adequate resources and the group is appropriately managed. Points to be checked are provided in Table 2.

Table 2: Points to be addressed when horses are group-housed

Points to address when horses are in groups

Is the group composition maintained to avoid disruption to the social hierarchy?

If new horses are introduced to the group, is it done gradually?

Are foals reared with mares and other foals?

Is weaning gradual (e.g. nutritional weaning before separation from the dam, foals maintained with adult or other foals) to minimise stress?

Are young horses kept with adult horses?

Is the lying area dry, clean, covered with bedding?

Is there enough space for all horses to lie down simultaneously in lateral recumbency with their limbs extended?

Is there enough space to reduce aggression and injuries (e.g. at least 330 m² per horse in a paddock)?

Is feeding space large enough to enable simultaneous feeding?

When horses are outdoor, is there protection against sun, bad weather, insects (e.g. shelter, fly mask)?

Is the housing designed to enable unimpeded access to resources such as feed, water, salt licks and minimise competition?

Are social interactions monitored to detect potential aggressiveness and risk of injuries?

Is there environmental enrichment (sensory, feeding, physical, or occupational enrichment)? See the **Thematic factsheet - Environmental enrichment for equines**

Is the environment (e.g. physical, social) predictable and controllable to reduce stress?

Observations of animals

Confinement can induce abnormal behaviours whereas group housing enables social interactions (aggressive or affiliative) between animals. Absence of abnormal behaviours and presence of affiliative rather than aggressive behaviours should be checked. The synchronisation of behavioural activities between horses is a sign of group cohesion.

1. **Prevalence of abnormal behaviours** (e.g. stereotypies (e.g. crib-biting¹ (Figure 2), weaving², pacing³), aggressiveness, withdrawn posture (Figure 3)) or related resource-based signs (e.g. presence of anti-weaving grids, tooth marks on stable door and feeding trough)
2. **Group cohesion**
 - a. Presence of affiliative interactions (e.g. allogrooming⁴, Figure 4)
 - b. Presence of aggressive interactions (e.g. bite or kick threat, bite, kick, attack, chase, fight)
 - c. Presence of injuries and skin lesions resulting from aggressive interactions

¹ The horse grasps a solid surface with its front teeth and pulls back, contracting the neck muscles and making a characteristic grunting noise.

² The horse repeatedly moves its head and neck from side to side, shifting its weight from one leg to the other.

³ The horse paces around the boundaries of a confined area.

⁴ Expressed by the parallel lateral position of the body of two horses, which allows nibbling along the back or withers of each horse

Figure 2: crib-biting

Figure 3: Withdrawn posture

Figure 4: Allo-grooming